

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

CURRENT PROBLEMS OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION MANAGEMENT: DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS

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Abstract. Inclusive education, recognized as a key factor of social equality and equity, is becoming an increasingly important priority in educational systems around the world. It involves creating conditions in which all students, regardless of their individual characteristics, including disability, ethnicity, language differences, and socio-economic status, have equal access to quality education and full participation in the educational process. The issue of inclusive education management in Azerbaijan remains an important and urgent issue in the country's education system. In recent years, the country has been actively developing inclusive education, which is part of a global trend aimed at ensuring equality in education. The relevance and expediency of studying this problem not only on an international scale, but also on the scale of our Republic is related to new trends in the education system. The purpose of this article is to analyze this problem from a comparative perspective, innovative trends in the management of inclusive education and its integration into the education system, which is a rather complex process designed to ensure access to education on the basis of

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

equal rights for all students with special educational needs. This process includes the adaptation of educational policies, curricula, teaching methods, and methods for evaluating the educational environment. One of the tasks that we have set for ourselves is to study international experience in this field and provide the international scientific community with experience in this area. The pilot project we have developed will not only introduce innovative technologies into the management of inclusive education, but will also create conditions for changing the system of introducing inclusion into the work of higher education, which will become a new approach to the education system for students with disabilities. The results obtained in the study of this problem allowed us to better understand the current situation, identify problems and develop effective strategies to solve them. Theoretically, this has made it possible to enrich the theory of education, which is associated with the possibility of opening up new perspectives in the areas of inclusive pedagogy and inclusive leadership.

Introduction

Inclusive education is one of the most important tools for ensuring the equal right to education for all children, including children with disabilities or other special educational needs. The World Health Organization has published statistics according to which about 15% of the world's population has a disability, and these data are constantly updated, which makes it necessary for us to regularly check reliable sources in order to receive the latest information. According to data from last year, there are about 63,000 children with disabilities in Azerbaijan. According to statistics, more than 90% of them are enrolled at the general education level. 75% study in general education institutions without special conditions; 25% study in institutions with special conditions (more than 3,000) and at home (more than 8,000). Several key documents serve as the basis for the development of inclusive education at the international level, in particular: the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2006), the Salamanca Declaration on Principles, Policies and Practices in the Field of Education of Persons with Special Needs (1994).

Inclusive education is defined as a process that shapes the culture, practices, and policies of the educational environment to meet the diverse needs of individual students while ensuring the elimination of barriers that limit students' access, participation, and achievements. UNESCO. (2020) It emphasizes the presence,

INCLUS INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

participation, and academic success of all students. Inclusion in higher education is summarized as a process of identifying and eliminating all barriers to ensure the presence, participation, and achievements of all students, with particular attention to student groups that may struggle to succeed, be marginalized, or excluded. Achieving inclusive education at all levels requires a broad understanding of inclusive education, along with leadership commitment to creating the right environment, establishing the appropriate culture, and implementing relevant policies and practices. This should permeate teaching and interactions, board meetings, teacher supervision, budget planning, and any engagement with the local community or the broader public.

Flexible curricula and adapted teaching and learning methods must be in place to accommodate the strengths, needs, and learning styles of individual students. Thus, educational institutions must ensure the early identification of students with disabilities and provide them with the necessary support. Such approaches commit to eliminating discrimination by offering personalized educational responses rather than placing the burden of adaptation on the student. Through appropriate training and professional development focused on inclusive pedagogy, staff in educational institutions should be equipped with the essential competencies to implement inclusive learning environments, ensuring problem-solving at the forefront of collaboration and teacher-student interactions. This enables teachers and instructors to adopt teaching methods that include all students.

Main part. Inclusive education, which underpins the concept of social inclusion, depends on the collaboration of multiple stakeholders. Understanding the connection between the learning environment and the broader community is essential for building inclusive societies. This requires dialogue among internal and external stakeholders, including university staff, students, government agencies, policymakers, the private sector, non-governmental organizations, and society as a whole. Additionally, awareness and knowledge about disabilities should be promoted through various associations, including teacher unions, student organizations, organizations for people with disabilities, and other school support groups. Through such partnerships, governments can mobilize the necessary human and financial resources to implement inclusive education goals. Achieving inclusivity in education is associated with

governance challenges, particularly regarding the equitable allocation of human and material resources needed to meet diverse learning requirements. In this regard, comparison, experience sharing, and resource distribution are other strong approaches to establishing inclusivity in higher education. Mechanisms and incentives should be developed to enable flexible resource transfers that ensure the availability of expert knowledge in both formal and informal educational institutions, thereby promoting inclusive education environments. Globalization and increasing competitiveness in the modern world depend on the quality of its human resources. Inclusive education enhances a country's global competitiveness by harnessing the potential of all people. The transition to inclusive education and, consequently, issues related to the management of these processes in Azerbaijan are relatively new. However, despite this, serious research is underway in our Republic in this area, new government documents have been adopted that regulate these processes in Azerbaijan and create conditions for further improvement of the mechanisms of its application, rules and standards of execution. In particular, it is important to clearly define the responsibilities and responsibilities of local executive authorities, educational institutions, and other stakeholders.

The National Strategy for the Development of human Capital is based on an established and constantly improving system of human potential formation, including through the development of education. Based on this policy of the state, comprehensive events are organized and conducted in the Republic aimed at implementing projects related to the phased introduction of inclusive education into the education system of Azerbaijan, which is embodied in joint projects of the Ministry of Education of Azerbaijan together with the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), international scientific and practical conferences are organized and held annually in Baku. topic: "Inclusive education: experiences and challenges ahead", the purpose of which is to share experiences between countries of the near and far abroad, The prospects for the development of this problem are being determined, and a program and an action plan are being jointly drawn up to address such a global problem as helping children with disabilities. I would like to emphasize that the merits of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation are invaluable in the implementation of this program, which has implemented a range of measures to support and assist in the organization of education for this category of children, strengthen the material,

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

technical and educational base of educational institutions in which they study. It is impossible not to mention the work of the Department of inclusive education at the Institute "Problems of Education", which develops methodological recommendations, textbooks, and programs necessary for working with children in this group.

Special attention should be paid to the large-scale activities carried out at Baku Slavic University, workshops, week-long seminars with invited guests, specialists from the centers who conduct educational seminars, discuss important practical issues related to the system of introducing inclusion into education, integration of inclusion into secondary schools, exchange of experience with students studying in the specialty. "Correctional education", "Psychology", "Social and psychological service in education", etc. A number of legislative and regulatory acts have been developed in Azerbaijan to implement inclusive education, which provide a legal basis for accessibility of education for children with disabilities and contribute to the introduction of an inclusive approach into the education system. Over the past five years, Azerbaijan has adopted several important documents aimed at developing inclusive education and improving access to educational services for children with disabilities. Here are some of them:

The State Program for Ensuring Equal Opportunities for People with Disabilities (2018-2024). The document was adopted with the aim of improving the social integration of people with disabilities, including through the education system. The program contains provisions aimed at improving the accessibility of educational institutions for children with special needs, as well as the introduction of inclusive educational practices in schools and other educational institutions.

The Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Social Services for People with Disabilities" (2019), which provides for improving conditions for people with disabilities, including providing them with access to quality education, as well as creating special conditions for teaching children with disabilities and developing adapted educational programs.

The decision of the Ministry of Education of Azerbaijan on the introduction of inclusive education (2020) Within the framework of this document, the Ministry of Education of Azerbaijan has approved a number of initiatives aimed at creating inclusive classrooms and improving conditions for children with disabilities. This

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

includes the training of teachers and specialists, the development of methodological materials and the adaptation of curricula for inclusive classrooms.

The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers on the establishment of special educational institutions for children with special needs (2021) is aimed at the creation and development of specialized educational institutions for children with severe developmental disabilities, as well as the integration of these institutions into the inclusive education system. The decree provides for the development of infrastructure, improving the availability of educational services and expanding the coverage of children with disabilities.

The Methodological Recommendations on Inclusive Education for Teachers (2021), developed by the Ministry of Science and Education in collaboration with other public and private institutions, include best practices for teaching children with various developmental disabilities, as well as methods of working with children with physical and mental disabilities.

A very important document was the "Strategy for the Development of Inclusive Education in Azerbaijan" (2022-2026), which includes the tasks of educating teachers, providing a barrier-free environment in educational institutions and improving educational materials for children with disabilities, providing for the active participation of parents and public organizations in the process of inclusion.

In 2023, the document "Updated National Standards for School Education" (2023) was adopted, which define how educational programs and educational materials for children with special needs should be adapted, as well as how inclusive classes should be organized. And of course, it is impossible not to mention the "Plan for improving digital technologies in education for children with disabilities" (2023), which includes the introduction of specialized programs and devices, such as adapted computer programs that allow children with hearing, visual or motor impairments to study in regular schools. The documents we have presented together form the basis for the further development of inclusive education in Azerbaijan and ensure the creation of the necessary conditions for the full participation of children with disabilities in the educational process.

There are certain difficulties in the implementation of these decisions, which include:

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

- a shortage and training of qualified personnel for the successful implementation of inclusive education (specially trained teachers, psychologists, speech therapists and other specialists are needed).
- Currently, the number of qualified personnel in this field is insufficient, and the issues of their training, retraining and advanced training remain relevant.
- Adaptation of the infrastructure of educational institutions, creation of the physical infrastructure of educational institutions (ramps, elevators, special equipment, etc.). Many educational institutions still lack such infrastructure.
- Shaping attitudes towards inclusivity in society: The success of inclusive education also depends on society's attitude towards this issue. In some cases, parents, teachers, and others oppose inclusive education for children with special needs. Therefore, it is important to promote the values of inclusivity in society and to carry out educational work in this area.
- Financing issues: The introduction of inclusive education requires additional funding. These funds should be spent on training qualified personnel, adapting infrastructure, purchasing special educational materials, and other needs.
- Weakness of the monitoring and evaluation system: it is necessary to create an effective monitoring and evaluation system for the implementation of inclusive education. This system should make it possible to measure the quality and coverage of inclusive education, identify problems and take measures to solve them.

For all these reasons, the issue of inclusive education management in Azerbaijan remains relevant and requires the implementation of systematic and comprehensive measures in this area. These measures should include improving legislation, training qualified personnel, adapting infrastructure, shaping attitudes towards inclusivity in society, increasing funding and strengthening the monitoring system. Clarifying the conceptual foundations of inclusive education involves accurately defining the meaning, scope, and basic principles of inclusive education. The formulation of this problem involves solving the following tasks.

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Literary Review. Consideration of this issue would be incomplete without a comparative analysis of the international contribution of scientists to the study of inclusion issues. Let's focus on the experience of several countries demonstrating different approaches to the development and management of inclusive education. One of the most developed inclusive education systems in the world is the Swiss one, which focuses on early detection and support of children with special needs, develops individual educational plans, has qualified teachers, has a well-developed support system for teachers and schools, as well as resources for the implementation of these programs.

If we note the features of inclusive education management, then there is a decentralized management system where responsibility for the implementation of inclusive practices is assigned to local municipalities. The strength of this inclusive education management model is strong government support, well-trained educators, a culture of acceptance and respect for people with special needs.

No less interesting is the Canadian system, where each province has its own approaches to inclusion and is responsible for financing and managing inclusive education. The key success factors are a strong legislative framework, financing, professional training of teachers, partnership with parents and public organizations.

In Germany, the right of a disabled child to choose an educational institution of

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

any type on an equal basis with everyone is legally confirmed. Children are accepted into both regular and specialized schools. The Law on Social Security establishes the rights of children with disabilities to receive rehabilitation assistance.

Governance in the UK is characterized by a centralized management system, but schools have significant autonomy in implementing inclusive practices, there is a system for evaluating the effectiveness of inclusive education, as well as a variety of approaches, from integrated learning to specialized schools.

The Italian management system deserves admiration, in which there are almost no specialized schools for children with disabilities, and the management has a centralized system where support teachers provide assistance to children with special needs in general education classes, which is undoubtedly due to a strong ideological commitment to the principles of inclusion.

General trends and successful practices in the management of inclusive education should be noted. Despite the differences in national models, there are several common trends and successful practices in the field of inclusive education:

- Early identification and support of children with special needs and providing them with the necessary support.
- Individual educational plans that take into account the individual needs and abilities of each student, adapting the curriculum and materials to the needs of students
- Training and support of teachers, providing them with the necessary knowledge, skills and resources to work with children with special needs.
- The use of modern innovative technologies, an online platform, can greatly facilitate the learning process for children with special needs.
- Creating an atmosphere of acceptance, respect and support where each student feels valued and needed.
- The analysis of international experience in the management of inclusive education opens up prospects for the further development of inclusive education, which are related to:
- Improving legislation, which implies the creation of a clear and comprehensive legislative framework that ensures the rights of children with special needs to education.

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

- The expansion of international cooperation, which involves strengthening international cooperation and the exchange of experience in the field of inclusive education.
- The need to increase investments in education, teacher training, the development of educational materials and the adaptation of infrastructure.
- Increasing the level of education and acceptance in society of the main provisions concerning the system of inclusive education.

In the inclusive education management system, innovative technologies play a very important role in creating a supportive learning environment and meeting the diverse needs of students. These technologies enhance the inclusivity of education, help develop the potential of each student, and provide support to teachers. Among the innovative technologies used in inclusive education, the following can be noted: Adaptive learning platforms that adapt to students' individual learning speed and style. With the help of artificial intelligence and data analysis, the strengths and weaknesses of each student are identified, and individual learning materials are provided to them. This creates more effective learning opportunities for students with different learning abilities in an inclusive environment. Augmented and virtual reality, AR and VR technologies offer students a more interactive and immersive learning experience. Speech and text converters (Speech-to-Text and Text-to-Speech): These technologies support students who have difficulty reading and writing. Speech-to-text converters convert what students say into text, while speech-to-text converters convert text into sound, helping them learn materials by ear. Communication assistants (Assistive Communication Technologies), technologies that support students with speech and communication difficulties. For example, alternative and advanced communication systems allow students to express their opinions through images, symbols, or text. Robotics helps to develop social skills, especially for students with autism, interacting with them interactively, allowing them to experiment with different social situations. An equally interesting tool is data analysis and artificial intelligence, technologies that help track students' progress, identify individual needs, and help teachers improve teaching methods. Online platforms for collaboration and communication, and of course, 3D printers that help make learning materials more accessible to students (sensor models and diagrams).

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Of course, the advantages of introducing innovative technologies into the inclusive education management system are beyond doubt, as learning opportunities appear that are adapted to the individual needs of students, motivation increases, results improve, and student academic performance increases. Therefore, innovative technologies are very important in the inclusive education management system to improve the quality of education, meet the individual needs of students and create a more inclusive learning environment. The proper use of these technologies will help all students reach their full potential. Higher education institutions, by embracing the principle of inclusivity, should create environments that support not only students' academic skills but also their social and psychological well-being. This will enable each individual to fully realize their potential and build a successful future career. Implementing inclusivity in higher education requires a systematic approach. Universities, government structures, non-governmental organizations, and society must collaborate to strengthen their roles in the inclusive education process. To create a more accessible and inclusive higher education system, it is essential to review the principles and strategies of inclusive education. Additionally, identifying emerging challenges and finding solutions to address them is crucial for the development of an inclusive education system.

Inclusive education remains one of the primary strategies that educational policy must implement. Inclusive education practices are based on recognizing and accommodating individual needs. Therefore, education should be organized to meet the unique needs of every individual. A unified database should be established to identify individuals with disabilities, track their health, rehabilitation, and educational progress, and ensure timely intervention if a program does not suit a particular individual. Given the number of individuals with disabilities in the country, inclusive education institutions should be identified, and comprehensive conditions should be provided for them. Moreover, higher education institutions should not only provide access to education but also create an environment that supports students' personal development and future success. More inclusive approaches should be implemented in education strategies to address these needs.

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Key Directions for Organizing Inclusive Education in Higher Education Institutions:

No	Direction	Detailed Description
1	Strategic Goals	- Establishing a fair educational environment that ensures equal opportunities regardless of disability, socio-economic status, or background .- Fostering students' self-confidence, independence, and career readiness .- Promoting values of diversity, equity, and inclusion across campus life.
2	Governance and Policy	- Integrating inclusive education as a core component of national and institutional education policies .- Establishing clear guidelines and accountability mechanisms for inclusion at all administrative levels.- Securing long-term funding models for inclusive education initiatives.
3	Infrastructure and Environment	- Ensuring universal design principles in all physical spaces (e.g., accessible classrooms, dormitories, libraries).- Equipping campuses with assistive technologies (screen readers, captioning software, etc.).- Designing inclusive digital platforms and e-learning tools with accessibility standards .
4	Academic and Psychological Support	- Developing Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) tailored to students' specific needs.- Establishing specialized disability support centers with trained staff.- Providing continuous mental health services , peer support groups, and academic counseling to prevent dropouts and foster well-being.
5	Professional Development of Staff	- Implementing mandatory training modules on inclusive pedagogy for academic and administrative staff.- Encouraging research and innovation in inclusive teaching methodologies.- Supporting international collaboration and mobility programs to exchange best practices in inclusion.
6	Awareness and Social Engagement	- Organizing campaigns, seminars, and inclusive events to challenge stereotypes and increase awareness among students and staff.- Facilitating the creation of student-led inclusive clubs and advocacy groups.- Building community partnerships to support real-life integration and internship opportunities.
7	Monitoring and Evaluation	- Setting clear indicators and KPIs to assess the success of inclusive practices.- Collecting regular feedback from students with disabilities , faculty, and parents.- Publishing annual inclusion reports to improve transparency, promote accountability, and guide data-driven decision-making.

Thus, the results of studying the problem of inclusive education management are not only of scientific importance, but also of great practical importance in terms of improving educational policy, ensuring the professional development of teaching staff, creating an inclusive school environment and more efficient allocation of resources.

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Research in this area contributes to building an education system in which all students have equal learning opportunities and can develop as full members of society. A lot of work is being done in Azerbaijan in this direction. In 2011, an international scientific and practical conference on "Inclusive education: experience and challenges ahead" was held in Baku. Speaking about the purpose of this conference, it should be noted the importance of holding such conferences that promote the exchange of experience between countries near and far abroad, determine the prospects for the development of this problem, and develop a joint program and action plan to address such a global problem as helping children with disabilities. In 2022, Baku Slavic University hosted the international scientific and practical conference "From Inclusive Education to an Inclusive Society."

The conference was attended by representatives of various universities, centers, specialists, responsible workers working in the field of special psychology and pedagogy, inclusive education and other relevant structures: Director of the Institute of Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan Rufat Azizov, Chief of Staff of the State Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Family, Women and Children Jeyran Rahmatullayeva, Chairman of the Public Association "Birgə və sağlam" Ayten Einalova, Chairman of the Public Association "World of Skillful Hands" Azad Mammadov, and others.

On April 02, 2022, the III International Conference "Autism ABA Azerbaijan" was held at the Heydar Aliyev Center, and on March 11, 2023, a congress for people with special needs was held at the Heydar Aliyev Center. The main and most important goal that the Congress is trying to achieve is to raise public awareness of people in need of special care, and most importantly, to help these people find their place in society. The Congress was attended by leading international experts from the USA, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Israel, Russia, Turkey and other countries. The leadership of Baku Slavic University has always shown a special interest in this area, which is included in the strategic plan of the university. The organization of International scientific and Practical Conferences "From inclusive education to an inclusive society", which have been organized over the past few years, is a prime example of this. In a short time, the university has created a platform for studying and discussing the problems facing

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

higher education institutions in the field of inclusive education, content management and the use of the latest learning technologies, the training of competent personnel, as well as the study of international experience in this area. Scientific seminars, master classes, presentations, and workshops are held within the framework of the conference with the participation of domestic and international experts on inclusive education.

Materials and methods. We have developed a pilot project "Program to support the education of students with disabilities", the main goal of which is to integrate inclusive students into university education. The implementation of this project involves going through several stages:

Stage I: Creation of a professional training platform, which involves solving the following tasks:

- Training of competent higher professional education personnel and retraining of the university's teaching staff involved in supporting inclusive education for the disabled and people with disabilities;
- Creation of a tutor support service: providing individual support to students with special educational needs, training tutors for students with disabilities (hearing impairments, use of sign language, etc.); creation of a tutoring system as a form of individualized accompanying education for people with disabilities;
- Training students in this specialty, providing continuous practice in centers, specialized schools to familiarize themselves with the work of specialists in this field;
- Creation of an office for conducting classes in correctional pedagogy and psychology (special equipment, stands for teaching students how to work with people with disabilities, tools for conducting art therapy lessons), a sensory room;
- Methodological support of special literature: educational didactic manuals, adapted game manuals,
- Conducting thematic training sessions (together with psychologists), seminars for students to replenish knowledge in this field, joint online classes to establish communication with students of other universities (in the Republic and abroad) with limited health opportunities.

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

in order to share experience in this area;

- Cooperation with other universities both in the republic and foreign universities
 - Creation of a website and its adaptation for students with disabilities: providing the ability to change the font size, contrast, and the use of on-screen speakers
 - Preparation and placement of educational material in audio and video format (in subjects that student's study), with information support, versions for visually impaired students, etc.;
 - Training of volunteers from among students studying in the specialty: "Correctional pedagogy", "Socio-psychological service in education", "Psychology" for providing psychological and pedagogical support to students with disabilities;
- Stage II: the introduction of inclusive education in higher education institutions
GOAL: to include young people with disabilities in the BSU continuing education system.

Tasks:

- Formation of the coordinating council of the university, the resource center for psychological and pedagogical rehabilitation of students with disabilities;
- implementation of a program for step-by-step inclusion of students with disabilities in the student environment, starting with pre-university one-year training, academic support;
- equipping educational institutions with special, including educational computer equipment (stationary, portable electronic video enlargers, FM systems / radio classrooms, the use of a Braille display); sensor room equipment:
- Creation of adapted curricula and educational materials for students with disabilities;
- modification of basic educational programs for bachelor's, specialist, and master's degrees, taking into account the individual educational needs of people with disabilities and people with disabilities;
- Creation of a resource center with access to global information resources;

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

The novelty of the project: The inclusion of young people with special educational needs (people with disabilities, with disabilities, with special needs) in the educational process at the university is a new approach for the education system of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Expected result: Confirmation of the effectiveness of the model is the competitiveness of graduates with disabilities in the labor market.

Discussion. The relevance of the problem, which has been the subject of our research for several years, puts us in front of the need to consider the ideas of scientists, their valuable contribution to global research conducted by the scientific community around the world.

Azerbaijani and Turkish scientists have made a definite contribution to the development of this problem. In the work of U.K.Alekperov (2019), valuable ideas are presented about the possibilities and prospects of sustainable inclusive development of Azerbaijan, new trends that are taking place in this direction. L.S.Amrakhly (2018), a practical psychologist, teacher, who in her professional activity tries not only to explore theoretical issues related to helping children with disabilities, but also implements in practice the tasks set to introduce students to learning how to work with this category of people. The works of L.B.Javadova (2018), N.G.Mammadbekov (2012), and T.M.Verdieva (2021) reflect practical experience working with children, adolescents, and youth, which focused not only on rehabilitation and integration, but also on the development of psychological and pedagogical foundations for supporting parents and educating them on the issues of inclusive education.

Of particular interest to us are the works of Al-Dababneh, K., and Al-Zbun, E. [2020], who devoted much of their research to the use of assistive technologies in the curriculum for children with special learning disabilities in conditions of inclusion. Emphasizing the role of teachers' professionalism in building inclusive education, researchers Ferreira, M. (2022) paid great attention to rehabilitation and the use of assistive technologies in the practical activities of specialists. A theoretical essay on inclusion and the role of teachers

Of great interest to us were modern studies by Augus A., Juliadharm M., and Jamaludin M. (2023), who presented the results of using the CIP model in evaluating

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

the curriculum of inclusive education, to evaluate and improve the process of integrating inclusion into education. This model includes several aspects that make it possible to effectively plan activities in this area.: The context, i.e. determining the need for inclusive education, assessing its level, identifying target groups, etc.

Input: resources are identified, opportunities for their use, and the development of inclusive strategies.

Process: Implementation of inclusive programs (trainings, monitoring and evaluation, problems and shortcomings are identified, adjustments are made.

Product: Outcome Assessment: The results of inclusive programs are evaluated, impact assessments are made, lessons are learned, and recommendations for future programs are developed.

The CIP model allows for a systematic and comprehensive assessment and improvement of inclusion in the inclusive process. This model helps individuals make decisions based on data, use resources effectively, and create equal opportunities for all members of the community.

Issues of inclusive education management were considered by Ashraf A., Zhu H., Rauf V. (2018), who shared their experience in applying the IEMES inclusive Education Management assessment system model in universities that teach students with special needs. Apriliani I., Pakhrudin A., Kodiri K. and Syafril S. (2024) also provided interesting information on the management of inclusive education, which gives us a basis for comparing international experience and creates conditions for its effective use in their professional activities.

An overview of individual issues that arise in the field of education in the context of inclusion, the integration of people with disabilities into higher education, the process of accepting and including people with disabilities in the learning environment, the use of innovative and assistive technologies in the educational process are beautifully highlighted in the works of such scientists as: Clavijo Castillo, R. G., and Bautista-Cerro, M. J.(2020), Correa A., Masuchi M., Beta N., Takiuchi L., Bianco B. (2019), Demattews D., Billingsley B., Mcleskey J. and Sharma U. (2020).

The economic context of inclusive education and gender issues in the management of inclusive education are reflected in the works of Asongu, S., Nnanna,

J., and Achanyi, P. (2020).

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Conclusion

Thus, we have attempted to consider certain aspects of the rather urgent problem of inclusive education. This article provides a comparative analysis of international experience in the field of inclusive education development and management. We will look at different approaches, strategies, and models used in different countries to identify common trends, successful practices, and potential challenges to building inclusive educational systems. The development and management of inclusive education is a complex and multifaceted process that requires a systematic approach, political will and the participation of all stakeholders. A comparative analysis of international experience shows that successful inclusion is possible with a clear legislative framework, sufficient funding, qualified teachers, active participation of parents and the community, and the creation of an inclusive educational culture. Despite the existing challenges, the prospects for further development of inclusive education are encouraging, and with proper efforts, educational systems can be created that ensure equal opportunities for all students, regardless of their individual characteristics.

Further research, which we intend to continue as part of the research in this area, is related to the following aspects:

- The implementation of a pilot project at the university, where our professional activities take place.
- Creation of an electronic database on the university for effective work with students.
- Evaluation of the effectiveness of various models of inclusive education.
- Development and implementation of innovative technologies for inclusive education.

Training of highly qualified personnel who have innovative methods in their

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

arsenal to work in this area

- Studying the impact of inclusive education on the social adaptation and
- integration of children with disabilities.
- Analysis of the economic aspects of inclusive education.

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INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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